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Social, Economic, and Environmental Dynamics Intersecting Small-Scale Fishery Communities in the Demak Regency of Indonesia

V2V Working Paper No. 2025-06

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September 2025

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How to cite:

Lister, M. (2025). *Social, Economic, and Environmental Dynamics Intersecting Small-Scale Fishery Communities in the Demak Regency of Indonesia*. V2V Working Paper 2025-06. V2V Global Partnership, University of Waterloo, Canada. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17095530>.

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V2V Global Partnership is supported by the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada under its Partnership Grant Program.

Social Sciences and Humanities
Research Council of Canada

Conseil de recherches en
sciences humaines du Canada

Canada

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Abstract

Small-Scale Fisheries (SSF) governance has historically excluded small-scale fishers from participating in decision-making processes, negatively influencing millions of livelihoods. Governance of SSF is complex due to interactions between users and the environment, both with varying influence on the social-ecological system. Indonesia is of particular importance for SSF governance due to its archipelagic structure, fishing culture and the direct link between economic viability and SSF. Indonesian SSF provide livelihood, nutrition, and food and economic security to millions of fishers. Indonesian SSF however face, illegal and unreported fishing practices, fishing location disputes, pollution, poor living conditions, declining fish stocks and extreme volatile weather conditions. Effective governance strategies of SSF that are able to adapt to dynamic conditions within Indonesian SSF are critically needed. This research study aims to explore the strength of adaptive co-management indicators present within SSF in Indonesia, and how current management of SSF can be transitioned into adaptive co-management, aiding in the transition of SSF from vulnerability to viability. Adaptive co-management is a governance approach that combines co-management and adaptive management, while integrating the practices of learn-by-doing, social memory, and social networks into governance proceedings. Over 100 small-scale fishers completed household surveys, with more than ten semi-structured interviews being conducted with institutional, governmental, and fishery leaders to determine adaptive co-management indicators intersecting each SSF. Results indicate adaptive co-management is an effective governance approach for complex social-ecological systems such as SSF. Adaptive co-management additionally provides an avenue to facilitate vulnerable to viable SSF transitions. Long-term institutional support, effective capital building, and social capital were identified as the strongest indicators of adaptive co-management, marking these indicators as critical for future development in SSF.

Keywords Social-ecological system • governance • adaptive co-management • sustainability • small-scale fisheries

1. Introduction

Coastal Small-Scale Fisheries (SSF) are complex and dynamic, often influenced by multilevel drivers. Effective governance is required to govern SSF. SSF operate using minimal technology and energy while fishing, fish in locally known waters, eat fish for consumption, sell fish within local markets, have fishing vessels less than 12 meters in length and have a total weight of less than 5 GT (gigatons) (Bakiu et al., 2018; FAO, 2015; Mozumder et al., 2020). SSF require specific governance strategies because they are highly vulnerable to social and ecological change (Dias et al., 2023; Nayak, 2014). Understanding the dynamic interplay between social, economic and environmental characteristics within SSF can aid in understanding the transition of SSF from vulnerability to viability.

SSF can be described as a commons. A commons is a dynamic and complex system, collectively shared by the diverse users that interact with it (Berkes, 2005; Nayak & Berkes, 2021; Ostrom, 1994). A commons

is a common-property resource source such as a fishery, where various actors interact with the resource at varying scales, either through subtraction or exclusion (Berkes, 2005; Ostrom, 1994; Schlager & Heikkila, 2011). Subtraction in a commons is when one user's subtraction from the resource influences the availability of the resource for the next user (Berkes, 2005; Ostrom, 1994). Excludability is when an organization or user excludes the access of users or limits the number of users that can directly benefit from the resource (Berkes, 2005; Ostrom, 1994). Commons are areas of governance contention due to diverse users interacting with the resources of the system all with varying intentions. Dilemmas arise within commons when the collective community cannot communicate effectively, establish collective use rules, and no overall enforcement authority regulating collective rules (Ostrom, 1994). The commons of fisheries can be explained as follows; fishers initially interact with a fishery, begin having successful harvests, leading to the expansion of more fishers harvesting from the fishery, however, increased harvest levels from the fishery will eventually lead to a downfall in the fisheries ability to naturally regenerate, creating a tragedy in this commons (Berkes, 2005; Berkes, 1985; Nayak & Berkes, 2021; Ostrom, 1994). A tragedy of the commons can be created within a commons three ways according to Berkes, (1985) and Ostrom, (1994); (1) when the users of the resource become economically incentivized and pursue private individual gains over the collective interests of the community, (2) when the SSF exhibits a pattern of utilization that exceeds its natural ability to regenerate, and (3) when the SSF is collectively owned by the general population. Tragedies within SSF lead to appropriation and technological externalities, and assignment problems (Berkes, 1985; Berkes, 2005; Ostrom, 1994). This makes the governance of SSF imperative as mismanagement can lead to commons dilemmas.

Along with being classified as a commons, SSF can be further classified as a complex social-ecological system. A complex social-ecological system is a human-environment system that contains human interactions along with environmental interactions on a consistent basis within the system (Ostrom, 2007). A social-ecological system has social interactions that influence the ecological interactions within the system, while also producing ecological interactions that influence the social interactions with the system (Berkes, 2011; Folke et al., 2005; Nayak, 2014). Nayak, (2014) outlines that social-ecological systems can be used to understand SSF, because issues are repeatedly occurring, complex, hard to define, and result from political, social, economic, and ecological factors. Major challenges that occur within social-ecological systems governance, identified by Nayak, (2014), are (1) institutional replacement, where powerful institutions take over the already established local institutions, (2) legitimacy, where new institutions lack local support and trust, (3) institutional disappearance, where powerful institutions engulf already established institutions, and (4) missing linkages between institutions are created. These challenges highlight the importance of effective governance within social-ecological systems.

Social-ecological systems governance heavily relies on effective participatory management approaches (Berkes, 2011), collaboration and learning (Berkes, 2011; Plummer et al., 2013), building adaptive capacity (Plummer et al., 2013), and the delineation between social and ecological interactions within the system (Folke et al., 2005; Nayak et al., 2016). To manage social-ecological systems effectively Folke et al., (2002) and Berkes, (2011) explain that governance requires the integration of local stakeholder knowledge and perspectives at various governance levels, helping improve knowledge at various cross scale linkages. To understand the complexity of SSF, identifying social, economic and environmental drivers within the system are crucial.

SSF can lastly be described through systems thinking. Systems thinking highlights the non-linear linkages that are interwoven in social and ecological interactions, providing indication when systems are vulnerable or in equilibrium (Armitage et al., 2007; Monat & Gannon, 2015; Nayak, 2014; Williams et al., 2017). Systems thinking is an efficient lens to understanding dynamic change occurring at various scales, through interconnected linkages, feedback, self-organization, and the adaptive capacity of communities (Armitage et al., 2007; William et al., 2017). To understand the complex system of SSF, social, economic and environmental characteristics that influence the system need to be understood.

Current governance of social-ecological systems, such as SSF, has been insufficient at addressing the vulnerabilities faced by small-scale fishers. Governance of SSF has historically excluded small-scale fishers from participation, strengthening vulnerabilities faced by fishers including competition, fish stock decline, and exploitation of fishery resources (Issac, 2013; Sowman et al., 2014; Mozumder et al., 2020). Current governance approaches for SSF will continue to exacerbate vulnerabilities for small-scale fishers as top-down management approaches are insufficient at addressing the diverse socioeconomic characteristics of fishers (Mozumder et al., 2020). Effective governance strategies for SSF therefore must be able to address the dynamic economic, social and environmental characteristics influencing small-scale fishers' viability.

Indonesia is of particular importance for SSF governance. Indonesia's population is heavily reliant on the production of SSF. In 2022 capture fisheries around the globe accounted for 92.3 million tons of aquatic species and Indonesia was the second highest contributor at 8%, behind China at 14% (FAO, 2024). Additionally, due to a high proportion of the Indonesian population relying on fisheries production, the consumption of fish has increased 34% from 1961 to 2021 (FAO, 2024). Over fifty percent of the Indonesian population's animal consumption comes from fish products (Warren & Steenbergen, 2021). Indonesia is also the largest archipelagic country in the world with over 17,000 island states, many directly reliant on the production of SSF. Additionally, Halima et al., (2019), notes that within Indonesia SSF require specific governance approaches due to the complexity of relationships of regulations, rules and norms intersecting these fisheries. Finding effective governance strategies for Indonesian SSF are vital to ensure viability of the Indonesian population.

Scholars such as Berkes, (2011), have noted that increased attention is required in SSF within social-ecological systems to determine effective governance. Identifying social, economic and environmental characteristics influencing SSF can aid in understanding the transition of SSF from vulnerability to viability. Vulnerability is defined by Dias et al., (2023), as the loss of community resilience and capacity for that same community to adapt and overcome future impacts, created by social, cultural, and ecological interactions (Dias et al., 2023). Viability within SSF is defined by Dias et al., (2023) and Nayak & Berkes, (2019), as the transforming of vulnerable fishing communities through increasing SSF abilities to navigate uncertainty, adapt to changing conditions, build resilience, create social capital and networks, and increase the working relationships of trust between users. Dias et al., (2023), notes understanding vulnerability to viability transitions within SSF needs increased research.

The objective of this paper is to identify the economic, social and environmental characteristics intersecting two SSF in Indonesia and determine the most influential characteristics within each community.

2. Methods

2.1 Sampling

During implementation of this paper two SSF were purposefully sampled to use as case study sites within Indonesia. Purposeful sampling as outlined in Creswell & Creswell, (2023), is when a researcher deliberately selects participants or research sites, that will allow the researcher to best understand the research objectives and answer the central phenomenon. The sampling criteria when purposefully selecting the SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo were:

- (1) Must be a community with at least 50% of its members being small-scale fishers.
- (2) The community must be relatively close to Semarang, Indonesia.
- (3) There must be co-management or collaborative management practices must already be established in the communities.
- (4) The communities must have connections to the Universitas of Diponegoro, Indonesia.

Based on this criteria the SSF of Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia, and Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia were selected.

After SSF were purposefully selected, observations and semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders were conducted. Observations were completed in public spaces in the two SSF, where there was no expectation of privacy. Leaders for the semi-structured interviews were purposefully selected within each SSF by meeting the following criteria:

- 1) Must be a leader (fishery, government, or academic) in the community.
- 2) Must be partnered with Tambak Bulusan or Purwoejo, Morodemak.
- 3) Must work with small-scale fishers in the community.
- 4) Must be in a current position of leadership for at least three years in their respective community.

Based on the purposeful sampling criteria, 12 fishery and institutional leaders were sampled in Tambak Bulusan (6) and Purwoejo (6).

2.2 Data Collection

First, observations in communal places within each SSF in Indonesia were employed to observe the social, economic and environmental dynamics intersecting the community. Qualitative observations are defined by Creswell & Creswell, (2023), as a researcher taking field notes of their observations in unstructured ways, typically in the form of open-ended responses. After observations, informal conversations and semi-structured interviews were conducted, they were coupled together to illustrate the social, economic, and environmental characteristics intersecting each SSF.

Figure 1 represents the economic, social, and environmental characteristics observed in Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia. While figure 2 represents the economic, social and environmental characteristics observed in Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia. Figure 1 and Figure 2 were both created from primary observational and interview data, coupled with Google Maps and Canva software allowing for an illustrative representation of the characteristics influencing the two sampled SSF.

Following initial observations in each SSF, in-depth semi structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders within each SSF were conducted. Semi-structured interviews all for a flexible interview format throughout the interview as topics and ideas can be explored as they arise, in either more detail, or passed upon by the researcher if deemed irrelevant, allowing the unexpected to be incorporated into the data collection (Knott et al., 2022). Semi-structured interviews were intended to validate the results discovered in observations and informal conversations, providing a strong understanding of the social, economic and environmental dynamics in each SSF.

Figure 1

Illustrative Survey of Economic, Social and Environmental Dynamics Intersecting the SSF of Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia

Source: Primary Observation & Interview Data, 2024

Figure 2

Illustrative Survey of Economic, Social and Environmental Dynamics Intersecting the SSF of Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia

Source: Primary Observation & Interview Data, 2024

3. Results

3.1 Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesian

Economic, social and environmental characteristics were discovered in Tambak Bulusan to help determine the various influences in the SSF. Understanding social, economic and environmental characteristics provide an understanding of influence these characteristics have on Indonesian SSF. Additionally, economic, social, and environmental characteristics were identified to aid in determining effective governance strategies for social-ecological systems such as SSF, increasing their viability.

3.1.1 Economic Characteristics

Economic characteristics of Tambak Bulusan were identified through firsthand observations and semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders in the SSF. The following tables represent the observed economic characteristics, and economic characteristics discovered in semi-structured interviews. Table 1 represents the economic characteristics that I observed intersecting the SSF of Tambak Bulusan. Table 1 identifies the economic characteristics being observed, the methods of how it was identified and an explanation of the observed economic influence.

Economic Characteristics	Method of Identification	Economic Influence
Fish Processing in Fisher Homes	Observations	Processing fish in fishers' homes increases fishers' economic livelihood by providing access to ship products to various Indonesian and Asian countries. Many of the processors are the wives of fishermen and the production of this processing is directly reliant on the production of the SSF.
Aquaculture Fishponds	Observations	Aquaculture fishponds are one of the alternative forms of livelihoods for small-scale fishers in Tambak Bulusan. Many small-scale fishers diversify their livelihood by also partaking in aquaculture fishing, along with marine capture fishing.
Tourism	Observations	Tourism has evolved in Tambak Bulusan due to its proximity to the Java Sea and the pristine beaches surrounding it. With declining fish stocks, tourism has served as an alternative livelihood for small-scale fishers. Fishers use their vessels to transport tourists.
Marine and Mangrove Fishing	Observations	This is the main form of capture fishing production in the community. The majority of small-scale fishers in this community are directly reliant on the production of these locations for their economic livelihood. Increased environmental damage to these locations is threatening fisher viability.
Fish and Boat Landings	Observations	Fish and boat landings provide an avenue for small-scale fishers to offload their fish catch and be transported to various locations in the community, including processing facilities, markets or fisher houses. These landings are the main locations for small-scale fishers to dock their boats between fishing trips as well.

(Source: Primary Observational Data, 2024)

Table 2 identifies the economic characteristics intersecting the SSF of Tambak Bulusan that were discovered in semi-structure interviews with fishery and institutional leaders. Table 2 identifies the economic characteristic, how it was identified, the number of total interview participants that mentioned it and the percentage of total interview participants that identified the characteristic.

Table 2			
<i>Economic Characteristics Intersecting Tambak Bulusan Identified from Semi-Structured Interviews</i>			
Economic Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristics	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Environmental Damage	Semi-Structured Interviews	5	83.33%
Declining Fish Stocks	Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Illegal Fishing Gear	Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Supply Chain Management	Semi-Structured Interviews	1	16.67%

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Table 3 identifies what fishery and institutional leaders within the SSF of Tambak Bulusan said when identifying each economic characteristic. Table 3 indicates the characteristics of focus, the leader in the SSF that mentioned it, and the quote of what the leader said in regard to the characteristic.

Table 3		
<i>Institutional and Fishery Leader Explanation of Economic Characteristics in Tambak Bulusan</i>		
Economic Characteristics	Interview Respondent	Quote
Environmental Damage	Community Tourism Leader	"Mangrove damage is our biggest obstacle, because our tourism concept is mangrove tracking and coastal panorama. So, if there is damage in the mangrove and coastal areas, the repair process will take a long time."
	SSF Leader	"There are several problems, starting from the weather, big waves, and floods. Because if there are these conditions, fishermen must stop fishing."
	SSF Leader	"There are several problems that cause a decrease in income, [...] Abrasion."
	Academic Institution	"(Tambak Bulusan) is facing environmental degradation problems, due to the impact of natural disasters."
	Local Village Government Leader	"Of course, it is related to climate and weather. In addition to natural conditions, currently, water quality is also decreasing."

Declining Fish Stocks	Academic Institution	"The community there faces problems in managing fisheries productivity, but there is still ecotourism to help alleviate the problem during the low season."
	Local Village Government Leader	"Currently, many factories are standing and dumping waste into the river. So, the fisheries ecosystem here is very affected, and very disturbed for the quality of the fish caught."
	SSF Leader	"This destructive fishing gear is the cause of the large number of fish stocks decreasing [...] Evidence 10 years ago before the massive destructive fishing gear, the community here could harvest fish with nets alone, reaching 100-150 kg in one trip to sea."
Illegal Fishing Gear	SSF Leader	"Currently, the development of fishing gear is increasingly rapid. This information can provide alternatives for new ways to catch fish."
	SSF Leader	"There are already regional regulations that bind the use of this fishing gear. But in its implementation, it has not been implemented effectively by the government."
	Local Village Government Leader	"In the past, the use of fishing gear was still very traditional, but now there are many types of fishing gear."
Supply Chain Management	Manager of Fish Processing and Trading	"We have difficulty getting raw materials for the processing. But we can still continue, but it will definitely be different if we don't get the right raw materials [...] Usually we buy fish from the market in Semarang."

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

3.1.2 Social Characteristics

Seen social characteristics of Tambak Bulusan were identified through firsthand observations, while unseen social characteristics were identified through semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders. Seen characteristics are the observable characteristics to outside observers, while the unseen characteristics are only understood through the understanding of community dynamics. The following data tables represent the observed social characteristics, and the social characteristics discovered in interviews.

Table 4 represents the observed social characteristics identified in the SSF of Tambak Bulusan. Table 4 identifies the social characteristic, how it was identified, and an explanation of the observed social influence of each characteristic.

Social Characteristics	Method of Identification	Social Influence
Pollution	Observations	Pollution is evident throughout the community and its waterways. Piles of garbage can be seen on the shores of waterways, in boats, and around houses in the community. Community members were also observed throwing trash into the main waterway in the community.
Small-Scale Fisher Living Conditions	Observations	The living conditions of small-scale fishers are subliminal. Fishers mainly live in concrete homes, with few windows or doors. Materials used to construct homes were observed to be concrete, metal sheets, and a variety of wood materials. Houses in this community are impacted by extreme weather conditions further impacting the living conditions of fishers.

(Source: Primary Observational Data, 2024)

Table 5 identifies the social characteristics discovered in semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders. Table 5 states the social characteristic, how it was identified, the number of interview respondents who mentioned it, and the percentage of total interview participants that mentioned the characteristic.

Social Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristic	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Pollution	Observation + Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Fishing Location Disputes	Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Small-Scale Fisher Living Conditions	Observation + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Table 6 identifies the social characteristics that were discovered in semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders and what they said regarding them. Table 6 states the social characteristic, what interview respondents mentioned it, and what the interview respondent stated about the characteristic.

Social Characteristic	Interview Respondent	Quote
Pollution	Local Village Government Leader	"In addition to natural conditions, currently water quality is also decreasing. Maybe because of waste produced by households and factories. Because currently many factories are standing and dumping waste into the river".
	SSF Leader	"If there is currently a more productive and environmentally friendly fishing gear, we will [...] reduce income pressure."
	Community Tourism Leader	"Problem of garbage, because Tambakbulusan has several rivers upstream(s), so that many piles of garbage from downstream settle in the area around the Tambakbulusan river".
Fishing Location Disputes	Academic Institution	"The conflict that occurs in fishing is about the location, so we help resolve the problem between communities so that there is no conflict in fishing areas".
	SSF Fishery Leader	"However, because in its development, many parties intervene in the management of tourism and operations"
	Community Tourism Leader	"All villagers who have boats can participate in the beach exploration/boat taxi business."
Small-Scale Fisher Living Conditions	Academic Institution	"Another conflict is about housing. Some housing around the river mouth is not legal. So, the management here is often constrained by this problem, therefore we together with the government and local communities are looking for solutions to provide decent and legal housing."
	SSF Leader	"Our group does not seem to get any benefit from the village development funds. Even though we have submitted several proposals, they were not responded to by the village government".

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

3.1.3 Environmental Characteristics

Environmental characteristics were observed and discovered by semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders. Table 7 indicates the environmental characteristics that were observed to be

intersecting the SSF of Tambak Bulusan. Table 7 states the environmental characteristics, how it was identified followed by an explanation of the observed environmental influence.

Environmental Characteristics	Method of Identification	Environmental Influence
Extreme Weather Conditions	Observations	Evident markings of water damage from variable water levels in the community were evident on the majority of fisher homes. Additionally, major thunderstorms and flooding were experienced and observed during data collection in this community.
Mangrove + Marine Fishing	Observations	Mangrove and marine fishing are the main forms of fisheries production for SSF in the community. Without access to these vital ecosystems SSF livelihoods would be negatively impacted. Increased variable weather conditions are threatening these vital ecosystems.
Water Pollution	Observations	Water pollution is a major issue in this community. Waterways are heavily polluted with residents in the community not diverting attention to the issue because there is little educational awareness about the environmental impacts of pollution.

(Source: Primary Observational Data, 2024)

Table 8 indicates the environmental characteristics discovered in semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders. Table 8 states the environmental characteristic, how it was identified, the number of interview participants that identified it, and the percentage of total interviews participants that mentioned the characteristic.

Social Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristics	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Declining Fish Populations	Semi-Structured Interviews	4	66.67%
Extreme Weather Conditions	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	4	66.67%

Mangrove + Marine Fishing	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
Water Pollution	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Table 9 indicates the responses of fishery and institutional leaders for each environmental characteristic that was discovered. Table 9 states the environmental characteristic, what interview respondents mentioned it, and what the respondent stated about the characteristic.

Table 9		
<i>Institutional and Fishery Leader Explanation of Environmental Characteristics in Tambak Bulusan</i>		
Environmental Characteristics	Interview Respondent	Quote
Declining Fish Populations	SSF Leader	"This destructive fishing gear is the cause of the large number of fish stocks decreasing. Even though there are already regional regulations that bind the use of this fishing gear."
	Local Village Governmental Leader	"In the past, the use of fishing gear was still very traditional, but now there are many types of fishing gear."
	Fish Processing & Trading Manager	"We have difficulty getting raw materials for the processing [...] Usually we buy fish from the market in Semarang. Because we already have suppliers from the fish market in Semarang, so we often get raw materials from there."
	Academic Institution	"The community there faces problems in managing fisheries productivity, [...] during the low season."
Extreme Weather Conditions	SSF Leader	"There are several problems, starting from the weather, big waves, and floods. Because if there are these conditions, fishermen must stop fishing"
	Community Tourism Leader	"One of them is tourism repair due to natural damage (abrasion and big waves). In addition, mangrove damage is our biggest obstacle."
	Local Village Governmental Leader	"Of course, it is related to climate and weather."
	Academic Institution	"Environmental degradation problems, due to the impact of natural disasters."
Mangrove + Marine Fishing	SSF Leader	"Evidence 10 years ago before the massive destructive fishing gear, the community here could harvest fish with nets alone, reaching 100-150 kg in one trip to sea."

	Academic Institution	"Rehabilitation program by planting mangroves from the beginning to mapping the right position in the planting."
Water Pollution	Community Tourism Leader	"The last is the problem of garbage because Tambak Bulusan has several rivers [...] so that many piles of garbage [...] settle in the area around the Tambakbulusan river."
	Local Village Governmental Leader	"Currently water quality is also decreasing."

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

3.2 Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia

Economic, social and environmental characteristics were discovered in Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia, to help determine the various influences on SSF. Additionally, economic, social, and environmental characteristics were identified to aid in determining effective governance strategies for Purwoejo SSF.

3.2.1 Economic Characteristics

Table 10 identifies the economic characteristics that were observed in Purwoejo SSF. Table 10 indicates the economic characteristic, how it was identified and an explanation of the observed economic influence of the characteristic.

Economic Characteristics	Method of Identification	Explanation of Influence
Fishing Vessel Repair	Observations	An operation performed by small-scale fishers when they are not fishing. This operation repairs small-scale and large-scale fishing vessels. Without this vital service in the community fishers would be unable to keep their vessels in seaworthy conditions.
Fish Auction	Observations	This auction only operates from 1 pm to 4 pm daily. This is where fishers sell their fish catch to a variety of stakeholders from within and outside of the community. This is one of the main ways of acquiring income for fish catch in the community.
Dry Fish Processing	Observations	Dry fish processing is an alternative livelihood for many SSF and women in the community. These fish processors buy from the fish auction, process the fish, then sell them to neighbouring Indonesian island states. Dry fish is also exported to neighbouring southeast Asian countries, including Malaysia and Singapore.
Fish & Boat Landing	Observations	The fish and boat landings are near the mouth of the Java Sea. This is where fish catch is offloaded and transported to auction, processing, or fisher homes. This is the main area where boats dock, and unload fish within the community, marking it a vital economic hot spot.

Fish Catch Shuttles	Observations	This is a job that has been created as a direct result of the fish landing location. The fish landing location is away from community houses in Purwoejo. These shuttles transport large quantities of fish for a small fee, creating the basis of their livelihood, while allowing fish catch to be transported to other locations away from the boat landing.
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(Source: Primary Observational Data, 2024)

Table 11 indicates the economic characteristics discovered in semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders in Purwoejo. Table 11 identifies the economic characteristic, how it was identified, the number of interview respondents that identified it, and the percentage of total respondents that mentioned the characteristic.

Economic Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristics	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Economic Subsidies	Semi-Structured interviews	4	66.67%
Fishing Gear Utilized	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
Aquaculture Pond Structure	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Table 12 indicates the institutional and fishery leaders' explanation of the economic characteristics discovered in semi-structured interviews. Table 12 identifies the economic characteristic, what leader identified it, and what the leader said about the characteristic.

Economic Characteristics	Interview Respondent	Quote
Economic Subsidies	Community Governmental Fishery Leader	"Fishermen who do not have a sailing permit, will not receive a recommendation to get fuel subsidies."
	SSF Leader	"Here at the moment, we only get fuel subsidy assistance, each member gets a fuel subsidy of 2 liters/per day."

	SSF Leader	"The current problem is the difficulty of accessing fuel oil for the ship's engine".
	Head of Women Fishers and Processors	"The most frequently encountered issues are sailing permit administration and fuel subsidy letters."
Fishing Gear Utilized	Community Governmental Fishery Leader	"Fishing gear that is not environmentally friendly usually provides more fish harvests in the sea than fishing gear that is in accordance with the regulations. So, from an economic perspective, it encourages people to also use fishing gear".
	SSF Leader	"Currently we are competing with environmentally unfriendly tools. [...] This tool allows almost all fish to enter the net, unlike our fishing gear."
Aquaculture Pond Structure	SSF Leader	"The ponds here that I know are not in the form of embankments. So, because of using that, the number of fish living in ponds (here on average milkfish ponds) is low, many die - compared to ponds made of soil."
	Academic Institution	"There are other problems in the sale of fishery products, especially the problem of fishponds. This problem is related to the management of fishery products."

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

3.2.2 Social Characteristics

Table 13 indicates the social characteristics that I observed in the SSF of Purwoejo. Table 13 identifies the social characteristic, how it was identified and then an explanation of the observed social influence of the characteristics on the community.

Social Characteristics	Method of Identification	Explanation of Influence
Fishing Gear Utilized	Observations	There is a variety of fishing gear used including gill nets, traps, trawl nets, and throw nets. There is a high degree of competition between fishers in this community due to disparities in

		fishing gear and fish catch production between fishing gear.
Housing Crisis	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	The housing for small-scale fishers is in a state of vulnerability. The majority of houses are made from concrete, metal sheets and other structural materials. Houses in this community are impacted by floods, water damage, and erosion of buildings due to inclement weather.

(Source: Primary Observational Data, 2024)

Table 14 indicates the social characteristics discovered in semi-structured interviews from the fishery and institutional leaders in Purwoejo. Table 14 identifies the social characteristic, how it was identified, the number of respondents that identified it, and the percentage of interview respondents that identified this characteristic.

Table 12			
<i>Social Characteristics Influencing SSF in Purwoejo Discovered in Semi-Structured Interviews</i>			
Social Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristics	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Competition	Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Government Regulations	Semi-Structured interviews	2	33.33%
Housing Crisis	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	1	16.67%

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Table 15 identifies the institutional and fishery leader explanations of the social characteristics discovered in semi-structured interviews. Table 15 indicates the social characteristic, based on what the leaders identified it as, and what they said about the characteristic.

Table 13		
<i>Institutional and Fishery Leader Explanation of Social Characteristics in Purwoejo</i>		
Social Characteristics	Respondent	Quote
Competition	Community Governmental Fishery Leader	"The number of fishermen here is around 300 people."

	SSF Leader	"The problem is like this, because fishermen here can have 2-3 fishing gear per boat. So, the total number of fishermen is around 300 people."
	SSF Leader	"Competition between fishermen, related to the differences in fishing gear used."
Government Regulations	Academic Institution	"Morodemak has a bigger problem, because the fishing community is very large."
	Head of Women Fishers and Processors	"There are various agencies that usually help in fisheries management, starting from the marine and fisheries service (province - district), the Marine and Air Police Corps, the environmental service, the local government (district). They have various tasks and authorities here in regulating the management of fish here."
	Community Governmental Fishery Leader	"The provincial government has the authority to regulate and manage marine resources from a distance of 0-12 miles, then the national authority is above 12 miles-200 miles (EEZ). While for land management (fish auction and fishermen) is the task of the district government."
		"In terms of supervision, there is good cooperation from the fisheries and maritime services, the Directorate of Water and Air Police, and also from the Indonesian Navy".
Housing Crisis	Academic Institution	"Fishing gear that is not environmentally friendly usually provides more fish harvests in the sea than fishing gear that is in accordance with the regulations."
		"It can be seen that on the coast of Morodemak, it is affected by high abrasion and erosion, and some households have to look for other places to live because of the impact."
		"Another conflict is about housing. Some housing around the river mouth is not legal. So, the management here is often constrained by this problem."

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

3.2.3 Environmental Characteristics

Table 16 indicates the environmental characteristics identified by observations in Purwoejo. Table 16 states the environmental characteristic, how it was identified, and an explanation of its environmental influence.

Environmental Characteristic	Method of Identification	Explanation of Influence
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Flooding	Observations	Due to proximity to the Java Sea Purwoejo experiences fluctuating water levels and floods. Water damage was evident on various small-scale fishers' homes throughout the community. Informal conversations with fishers stated that water levels have been steadily increasing with no sign of stopping.
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(Source: Primary Observational Data, 2024)

Table 17 indicates the environmental characteristics that were discovered in semi-structured interviews with fishery and institutional leaders in Purwoejo. Table 17 states the environmental characteristic, how it was identified, the number of interview respondents that noted it, and the total percentage of interview respondents that identified the characteristic.

Environmental Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristics	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Dynamic Weather Conditions	Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Flooding	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
Soil Sedimentation	Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
Fishing Gear Utilized	Semi-Structured Interviews	1	16.67%

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

Table 18 indicates the environmental characteristics discovered by fishery and institutional leaders from semi-structured interviews. Table 18 identifies the environmental characteristic, the leader that mentioned it, and what the leader said about the environmental characteristic.

Environmental Characteristics	Interview Respondent	Quote
Dynamic Weather Conditions	SSF Leader	"The fishing community here has long experience in dealing with extreme weather that often occurs in November – February."
	SSF Leader	"Every morning, many of the nets are damaged every time there is a tidal wave."
	Academic Institution	"It can be seen that on the coast of Morodemak, it is affected by high abrasion and erosion."
Flooding	SSF Leader	"This area can experience rough and high-water levels every 2 weeks. This can also be seen from the shoulder of the road here, now it is high, in the past water often flooded the road here, even entering the house."

	Community Governmental Fishery Leader	"The Morodemak tridesa area is an area affected by abrasion and accretion, so that many coastal ecosystems (for example: mangroves) have been damaged a lot."
Soil Sedimentation	Academic Institution	"The Morodemak area is an estuary area, where there is a lot of sedimentation. The community there needs to think about how to solve the sedimentation problem to make it easier for their boats to dock on the shore."
	Community Governmental Fishery Leader	"Collaboration is carried out from the national level to the village level, from the national government side, contributing from the budget to solve these problems, starting from sedimentation, rehabilitation, and mangroves."
Fishing Gear Utilized	Community Governmental Fishery Leader	"There are already existing limitations to divide the fishing lanes of each fishing gear. So that there is no massive damage to the marine ecosystem."

(Source: Primary Semi-Structured Interview Data, 2024)

3.3 Economic, Social and Environmental Characteristic Comparison Between SSF

Table 19 indicates the summary and comparison of the economic, social and environmental characteristics identified in the SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia. Table 19 identifies each respective characteristic, how it was identified, how many interview respondents mentioned them, and the total percentage of interview respondents that noted the characteristic. Cells that are represented with "N/A" relate to characteristics that were discovered through observations and not interviews.

Table 19			
<i>Summary of Economic, Social and Environmental Characteristics Influencing SSF in the Demak region of Indonesia</i>			
SSF of Tambak Bulusan, Demak, Indonesia			
Economic Characteristics			
Economic Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristic	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Environmental Damage	Semi-Structured Interviews	5	83.33%
Declining Fish Stocks	Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Illegal Fishing Gear.	Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Supply Chain Management	Semi-Structured Interviews	1	16.67%
Fish Processing in Fisher Homes	Observations	N/A	N/A
Aquaculture Fishponds.	Observations	N/A	N/A
Tourism	Observations	N/A	N/A

Marine and Mangrove Fishing	Observations	N/A	N/A
Fish and Boat Landing	Observations	N/A	N/A
Social Characteristics			
Social Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristic	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Pollution	Observation + Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Fishing Location Disputes	Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Small-Scale Fisher Living Conditions	Observation + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
Environmental Characteristics			
Environmental Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristic	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Declining Fish Populations	Semi-Structured Interviews	4	66.67%
Extreme Weather Conditions	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	4	66.67%
Mangrove + Marine Fishing	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
Water Pollution	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
SSF of Purwoejo, Morodemak, Demak, Indonesia			
Economic Characteristics			
Economic Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristic	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Economic Subsidies	Semi-Structured interviews	4	66.67%
Fishing Gear Utilized	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
Aquaculture Pond Structure	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
Fishing Vessel Repair	Observations	N/A	N/A
Fish Auction	Observations	N/A	N/A
Dry Fish Processing	Observations	N/A	N/A
Fish & Boat Landing	Observations	N/A	N/A
Fish Catch Shuttles	Observations	N/A	N/A
Social Characteristics			
Social Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristic	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Competition	Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Government Regulations	Semi-Structured interviews	2	33.33%

Housing Crisis	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	1	16.67%
Fishing Gear Utilized	Observations	N/A	N/A
Environmental Characteristics			
Environmental Characteristics	Method of Identification	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristic	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
Dynamic Weather Conditions	Semi-Structured Interviews	3	50%
Flooding	Observations + Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
Soil Sedimentation	Semi-Structured Interviews	2	33.33%
Fishing Gear Utilized	Semi-Structured Interviews	1	16.67%

(Source: Primary Research Data, 2024)

4. Discussion

Results indicate that there are a variety of economic, social and environmental characteristics intersecting the two SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo (see Table 9). Identifying these characteristics can aid in classifying these SSF as social-ecological systems, drafting effective governance, and understanding the vulnerability to viability transitions of SSF further.

4.1 Understanding Indonesian SSF as Social-Ecological Systems

Through the identification of economic, social and environmental characteristics in the SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo (see Table 9), these SSF can be further classified as social-ecological systems. It can be seen in Table 9 in both SSF that social behaviors, such as fishing gear or cultural norms, are influenced by and influence environmental and economic dynamics within the SSF. While Table 9 also exemplifies environmental behaviors, such as extreme weather and flooding that are influenced by and influence social and economic dynamics in both SSF. Table 9 additionally exemplifies economic behaviors that are influenced and can influence environmental and social dynamics within the two SSF. These interactions can classify SSF as social-ecological systems.

The SSF of Tambak Bulusan can be classified as a social-ecological system due to the complexity of social (see Table 5) and environmental characteristics (see Table 8) intersecting and influencing each other. The SSF of Purwoejo can also be classified as a social-ecological system due to its complex social (see Table 13 & 3.14) and environmental characteristics (see Table 17) influencing each other within the system.

Therefore, using a social-ecological systems lens to examine the interworking's and dynamics of Indonesian SSF can help provide clarity on the process intersecting SSF and what possible outcomes and solutions could be discovered. Additionally, classifying the SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo as social-ecological systems can aid in understanding the complexity of interactions between social, economic, and environmental interactions within the system. Through the classification of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo as social-ecological systems governance strategies for SSF can become increasingly informed of the economic, social and environmental factors that influence the dynamic systems of SSF.

4.2 Clarity on SES characteristics facilitate SSF Governance

Identifying economic, social and environmental characteristics intersecting the SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo can aid in drafting effective social-ecological system governance. Berkes, (2011) stated that there is a need to bring more attention to SSF governance and how it can be effective. Through the identification (see Table 9) and mapping (see Figure 1 & 2) of the economic, social and environmental characteristics, governance strategies for SSF can become increasingly informed of the conditions that influence viability. This can allow for effective governance strategies to be drafted for SSF as all economic, social and environmental factors that influence the system are identified and understood.

Table 20 explains the most pressuring economic, social and environmental vulnerabilities being faced by SSF in Tambak Bulusan. Table 20 states the importance rank of the characteristic, whether it is social, economic, or environmental, what the characteristic is, the number of interview respondents that identified it, and the total percentage of interview respondents that mentioned the characteristic.

Table 1				
<i>Ranking of the Most Important Economic, Social and Environmental Characteristics in Tambak Bulusan</i>				
Rank.	Economic, Social or Environmental	Characteristic	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristic	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
1	Economic	Environmental Damage	5	83.33%
2	Environmental	Declining Fish Populations	4	66.67%
2	Environmental	Extreme Weather Conditions	4	66.67%
3	Economic	Declining Fish Stocks	3	50%
3	Economic	Illegal Fishing Gear	3	50%
3	Social	Pollution	3	50%
3	Social	Fishing Location Disputes	3	50%

(Source: Primary Research Data, 2024)

Table 21 additionally, states the most pressuring economic, social and environmental vulnerabilities being faced by small-scale fishers within Purwoejo. Table 21 states the importance rank of the characteristic, whether it is social, economic, or environmental, what the characteristic is, the number of interview respondents that identified it, and the total percentage of interview respondents that mentioned the characteristic.

Table 2				
<i>Ranking of the Most Important Economic, Social and Environmental Characteristics in Purwoejo</i>				
Rank.	Economic, Social, Environmental	Characteristic	Number of Respondents Identifying Characteristic	Percentage of Total Interview Respondents
1	Economic	Economic Subsidies	4	66.67%

2	Environmental	Dynamic Weather conditions	3	50%
2	Social	Competition	3	50%

(Source: Primary Research Data, 2024)

Identifying the top economic, social and environmental characteristics and vulnerabilities within Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo can aid in the facilitation of viable transitions within SSF. By understanding the most important vulnerabilities intersecting SSF socially, economically and environmentally policy can be tailored to the context specific needs of fishers in these communities. Identifying economic, social and environmental characteristics can help SSF navigate times of uncertainty through adaptation and resilience because policies are tailored to the community context. This is crucial to create viability as stated by Dias et al., (2023) and Nayak & Berkes, (2019), who explain increasing SSF abilities to navigate uncertainty, adapt to changing conditions and build resilience can increase the viability of SSF.

The identification of economic, social and environmental characteristics can aid in understanding the vulnerability to viability transitions of SSF. This is vital as scholars such as Dias et al., (2023), have noted that increased awareness and understanding is needed of how the facilitations of vulnerable to viable transitions can occur within SSF.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, this paper classified SSF in Indonesia as social-ecological systems, brought increased attention to the characteristics influencing the governance of SSF in Indonesia, and identify pathways to viability from vulnerability for Indonesia SSF. The objective of this paper was to identify the economic, social and environmental characteristics intersecting two SSF communities in the Demak region of Indonesia determining the most influential characteristics within each community. Economic, social and environmental characteristics were mapped (see Figure 1 and Figure 2) and discovered (see Table 9) within the SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo. Through the mapping and discovery of economic, social and environmental characteristics influencing the SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo, progress can be made towards increasing SSF viability.

The variety of social, economic and environmental dynamics intersecting the SSF of Tambak Bulusan and Purwoejo represent the vast influences that SSF faces on a daily basis. Understanding and addressing the most influential dynamics provide avenues for viable livelihoods for small-scale fishers in Indonesian SSF. Additionally, avenues for viable policy and institutional support can be created for vulnerable communities such as SSF with the inclusion of economic, social and environmental dynamics. Further research on how economic, social and environmental characteristics are faced differently by gender in SSF can provide alternative ways to identify and address vulnerabilities and influential factors in SSF.

References

- Armitage, D., Berkes, F., & Doubleday, N. (2007). Introduction: Moving Beyond Co-Management. In *Adaptive Co-Management: Collaboration, Learning, and Multi-Level Governance* (pp. 1–15). essay, UBC Press. Retrieved from https://books.scholarsportal.info/en/read?id=/ebooks/ebooks0/gibson_crkn/2009-12-01/7/420108#page=32
- Bakiu, R., Cakalli, M., Korro, K., Di Franco, A., & Guidetti, P. (2018). Small-scale fisheries at an Albanian marine protected area: A collaborative attitude is associated with higher catches. *Marine and Coastal Fisheries*, 10(6), 527–535. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mcf2.10036>
- Berkes, F. (1985). Fishermen and ‘The Tragedy of the Commons.’ *Environmental Conservation*, 12(3), 199–206. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892900015939>
- Berkes, F. (2005). Commons Theory for Marine Resource Management in a Complex World. *SENRI Ethnological Studies*, (67), 13–31. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.15021/00002658>
- Berkes, F. (2011). Restoring Unity: The Concept of Marine Social-Ecological Systems. In R. E. Ommer, R. I. Perry, K. Cochrane, & P. Cury (Eds.), *World Fisheries* (1st ed., pp.9–28). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444392241.ch2>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (6th ed.). Sage Publications Inc.
- Dias, A. C. E., Armitage, D., Nayak, P. K., Akintola, S. L., Arizi, E. K., Chuenpagdee, R., Kumar Das, B., Diba, S. A., Ghosh, R., Isaacs, M., Islam, G. M. N., Kane, A., Li, Y., Manase, M. M., Mbaye, A. A., Onyango, P., Pattanaik, S., Sall, A., Susilowati, I., ... Singh, S. (2023). From vulnerability to viability: A situational analysis of small-scale fisheries in Asia and Africa. *Marine Policy*, 155, 105731. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105731>
- Folke, C., Hahn, T., Olsson, P., & Norberg, J. (2005). ADAPTIVE GOVERNANCE OF SOCIAL-ECOLOGICAL SYSTEMS. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 30(1), 441–473. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.energy.30.050504.144511>
- Folke, C., Carpenter, S., Elmqvist, T., Gunderson, L., Holling, C. S., & Walker, B. (2002). Resilience and Sustainable Development: Building Adaptive Capacity in a World of Transformations, 437–440. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4315276>
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (Ed.). (2015). *Voluntary guidelines for securing sustainable small-scale fisheries in the context of food security and poverty eradication*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2024. (2024). FAO. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cd0683en>
- Halim, A., Wiryawan, B., Loneragan, N. R., Hordyk, A., Sondita, M. F. A., White, A. T., Koeshendrajana, S., Ruchimat, T., Pomeroy, R. S., & Yuni, C. (2019). Developing a functional definition of small-scale fisheries in support of marine capture fisheries management in Indonesia. *Marine Policy*, 100, 238–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.11.044>
- Isaacs, M. (2013). Small-scale Fisheries Governance and Understanding the Snoek (Thyrsites atun) Supply Chain in the Ocean View Fishing Community, Western Cape, South Africa. *Ecology and Society*, 18(4), art17. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05863-180417>
- Knott, E., Rao, A. H., Summers, K., & Teeger, C. (2022). Interviews in the social sciences. *Nature Reviews Methods Primers*, 2(1), 73. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-022-00150-6>

- Monat, J. P., & Gannon, T. F. (2015). What is Systems Thinking? A Review of Selected Literature Plus Recommendations. *Journal of Systems Science*, 4(1), 11–26. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.ajss.20150401.02>
- Mozumder, M. M. H., Pyhälä, A., Wahab, Md. A., Sarkki, S., Schneider, P., & Islam, M. M. (2020). Governance and Power Dynamics in a Small-Scale Hilsa Shad (*Tenualosa ilisha*) Fishery: A Case Study from Bangladesh. *Sustainability*, 12(14), 5738. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12145738>
- Nayak, P. K. (2014). The Chilika Lagoon Social-Ecological System: An Historical Analysis. *Ecology and Society*, 19(1), art1. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05978-190101>
- Nayak, P. K., & Berkes, F. (2019). Interplay Between Local and Global: Change Processes and Small-Scale Fisheries. In *Transdisciplinarity for Small-Scale Fisheries Governance* (Vol. 21, pp. 203–220). Springer.
- Nayak, P. K., Armitage, D., & Andrachuk, M. (2016). Power and politics of social–ecological regime shifts in the Chilika lagoon, India and Tam Giang lagoon, Vietnam. *Regional Environmental Change*, 16(2), 325–339. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-015-0775-4>
- Nayak, P. K., & Berkes, F. (2021). Framing Commons as a Process the Rudiments of Commonisation and Decommonisation. In *Making Commons Dynamic* (pp. 3–23). Routledge and Taylor & Francis Group.
- Ostrom, E., Gardner, R., & Walker, J. (1994). *Rules, Games, and Common-Pool Resources*. The University of Michigan Press.
- Ostrom, E. (2007). A diagnostic approach for going beyond panaceas. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(39), 15181–15187. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0702288104>
- Plummer, R., Armitage, D. R., & De Loë, R. C. (2013). Adaptive Comanagement and Its Relationship to Environmental Governance. *Ecology and Society*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05383-180121>
- Schlager, E., & Hiekkilä, T. (2011). Left High and Dry? Climate Change, Common-Pool Resource Theory, and the Adaptability of Western Water Compacts. *American Society for Public Administration*, 71, 461–470. <https://onlinelibrary-wiley-com.proxy.lib.uwaterloo.ca/doi/pdf/10.1111/j.1540-6210.2011.02367.x>
- Sowman, M., Sunde, J., Pereira, T., Snow, B., Mbatha, P., & James, A. (2021). Unmasking governance failures: The impact of COVID-19 on small-scale fishing communities in South Africa. *Marine Policy*, 133, 104713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104713>
- Warren, C., & Steenbergen, D. J. (2021). Fisheries decline, local livelihoods and conflicted governance: An Indonesian case. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 202, 105498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2020.105498>
- Williams, A., Kennedy, S., Philipp, F., & Whiteman, G. (2017). Systems thinking: A review of sustainability management research. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 148, 866–881. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.02.002>

Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Global Partnership

The Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) project is a transdisciplinary global partnership and knowledge network. Our aim is to support the transition of small-scale fisheries (SSF) from vulnerability to viability in Africa and Asia. Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. We use the term viability not just in its economic sense but also to include its social, political, and ecological dimensions.

The V2V partnership brings together approximately 150 people and 70 organizations across six countries in Asia (Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand), six countries in Africa (Ghana, Malawi, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania), Canada and globally. This unique initiative is characterized by diverse cultural and disciplinary perspectives, extensive capacity building and graduate student training activities, and grounded case studies from two regions of the world to show how and when SSF communities can proactively respond to challenges and creatively engage in solutions that build their viability. Further information on the V2V Partnership is available here: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org.

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